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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report, titled 'Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan', aims to design the strategy, plan and activities to be implemented under the HortiFoodTrends project, with the goal to maximise the project's visibility and impact. This is a living document that will be updated and adjusted on M17 and at the end of the project (M36).

With the overall project aim of strengthening the scientific excellence and innovation capacity of InHort in the field of novel food product development, considering the needs of the end user, by establishing a long-lasting, interdisciplinary collaboration network, activities described here focus on:

- creating visibility and raising awareness among all target audiences during the project;
- sharing knowledge and findings developed within the project;
- identifying exploitable results from HortiFoodTrends and working on their utilisation after the project.

TABLE OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Abbreviation	Meaning
CA	Consortium Agreement
CPPO	HortiFood Processing Centre
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
DCE	Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation
ESR	Early Stage Researchers
GA	The General Assembly
GDPR	The General Data Protection Regulation
IP	Intellectual property
IPR	Intellectual property rights
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
NCPs	National Contact Points
R&I	Research and Innovation
REA	European Research Executive Agency
ROI	Return on Investment
SME	Small and medium enterprises
TL	Task leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
WPLG	Work Package Leaders Group

1. INTRODUCTION

The present deliverable details the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DCE) Plan for HortiFoodTrends. Its main objective is to provide partners with a set of guidelines, responsibilities, and timelines for effectively disseminating the project in a strategic and targeted manner.

DCE Plan lists all planned dissemination and communication activities, tools, and channels. It matches them with target stakeholder categories and key performance indicators (KPIs) that will be used to evaluate the planned activities. The exploitation chapter explains the project's approach and strategy to make the best use of the project results, further maximise the project's impact and ensure the sustainability of its major activities, outcomes and developed tools, even after its end.

This plan was developed during the first six months of the project and is part of WP6 – Dissemination, communication and exploitation. It is a living document that will be regularly updated. The implementation, management and support of the DCE Plan will be coordinated by leader of WP6 - InHort, with the active participation of all partners.

According to the grant agreement, beneficiaries of the Horizon Europe projects have a legal obligation to engage in dissemination, exploitation and communication activities to spread the research results and maximise the impact of their project.

According to Grant Agreement, the beneficiaries of the Horizon Europe projects have a legal obligations to be engaged in activities of dissemination, exploitation, and communication. The general concept of these activities is described below in *Błąd! Nie można odnaleźć źródła odwołania..*

Table 1: Definitions of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation in Horizon Europe

COMMUNICATION Inform, promote and communicate activities and results	DISSEMINATION Make knowledge and results publicly available free-of-charge	EXPLOITATION Make concrete use of results for commercial, societal and political purposes
For Whom Citizens, stakeholders and the media	For Whom For those who can learn and benefit from the results, such as: scientist, industry, public authorities, policymakers, civil society	For Whom For those who can take the results forward or invest in them, such as: researchers, stakeholders, industry (also SMEs), public authorities, policymakers, civil society
How <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Having a well-designed strategy ✓ Conveying clear message ✓ Using the right channels 	How Public results in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Scientific magazines ✓ Scientific and/or targeted conferences ✓ Databases 	How <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Creating roadmaps, prototypes, software ✓ Sharing knowledge, skills, data
When <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ From the start until the end of action 	When <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Anytime, as soon as results become available ✓ Up to four years after the end of the project 	When <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Towards the end of the action and beyond, as soon as exploitable results are available

		✓ Up to four years after the end of the project
Why ✓ Engage with stakeholder ✓ Attract the best expert ✓ Raise awareness of how public money is spend ✓ Show the success of the European collaborations	Why ✓ Maximise the impact of the action ✓ Allow other researchers to go a step forward ✓ Contribute to the advancements of world class knowledge ✓ Make scientific results a common good	Why ✓ Lead to new legislation or recommendations ✓ For the benefit of innovation, the economy and society ✓ Help to tackle a problem and respond to an existing demand
It is a legal obligation! Article 17 of GA	It is a legal obligation! Article 17 of GA	It is a legal obligation! Annex 5: Specific Rules and Article 16 of GA

Source: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/58ad3394-0a63-11ee-b12e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>.

2. TARGET GROUP AND KEY MESSAGES

Stakeholder mapping is key to developing an effective dissemination and engagement strategy and supporting a viable exploitation plan. Before undertaking any dissemination/communication activities, it is crucial to think about specific target groups in order to tailor messages to the relevant groups and their specific needs. Understanding their needs and priorities allows for effective planning of DC activities, reach, and involve the right external players in the execution of the project and its post-action planning. In particular, for effective dissemination/communication, it is necessary to analyse each target group, taking into account their different concerns, capacities and interests (Who are they? What is their interest in our project? What are they thinking now? What do we want them to think?).

PROJECT PARTNERS

The direct beneficiaries of the project will be the staff of the project partners directly involved in the activities, followed by the entire community of partner institutions and the institutions themselves.

What do we want to achieve by reaching this target group?

InHort:

- improve research, administrative and management capabilities of InHort staff to conduct excellent research and generate innovation for the benefit of society and the economy. Developing research capacity will ensure career advancement and contribute to enhancing academic issue fulfilment.
- strengthen InHort's international position as a leading European centre for research and innovation in the agri-food sector. InHort will gain status word-class excellence research center to apply the research results in the field of novel HortiFood products development, considering the needs of the end-users with using the Living Lab approach.
- contribute to specific scientific advances, across and within disciplines of science of agriculture and horticulture as well as nutrition and food technology, including the use of models, algorithms and other state-of-art techniques in the sensory evaluation of food products and consumer research.
- expand research network connected with increased mobility in an international arena.

All project partners:

- make use of joint publications and projects, joint developed new innovative products or services; enrich PhD project (ESR, InHort), sharing PhD student projects (all);
- identify a current HortiFoodTrends: end-user expectation and response towards novel HortiFood products;
- provide access of semi-industrial equipment HortiFood Processing Center fostering creating innovation, provide access to diversified InHort raw material resources;
- stimulate common research, commercial opportunities, knowledge exchange by establish a long-lasting collaboration;
- possess an additional source of science funding.

Key message: Creating opportunities for gaining the competences as a top-class researcher; developing a successful network in the field of designing and commercialization of novel, end-user oriented, HortiFood products with potential to increase F&V consumption

Communication message:

“Join our capacity-building project to enhance your research skills, expand your network, and advance your career as a PhD student or young researcher. We offer comprehensive training and support to help you succeed in your field.”

“Collaborate with fellow researchers in our capacity-building project and take your work to new heights. Join a dynamic community of scholars to share knowledge, enhance skills, and produce impactful research. Our project offers a unique opportunity to strengthen connections and tackle complex challenges together.”

“Empower Your Research Administration Management Skills: Join Our Collaborative Capacity Building Project.”

DC activities and tools: All, in particular: Project website, Newsletter, Social Media, Project Conference, Events organisations.

SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY – EXTERNAL AUDIENCE

Relevant Research Centres and Universities (like the Association for Consumer Research (ACR) or the Institute related to Food Technologists (IFT) interested in the project results which could be useful for their own research activities, and also as a basis for further research in their fields.

What do we want to achieve by reaching this target group?

- Make use of the data collected during the project in the form of research documents, reports and resources;
- Increase the reputation of InHort as trustworthy partner for fruitful collaborations; establishing future cooperation and knowledge exchange;
- Providing access of semi-industrial equipment HortiFood Processing Center facilities to foster innovation; providing access to diversified InHort raw material resources;
- Promote the project and its results;
- Engage scientists in the project activities.

Key message: access to data collected during the project, possible future collaborations, access to the infrastructure (CPPO).

Dissemination message:

“Our capacity-building project for early stage researchers has successfully trained and supported a diverse group of researchers from around the world. Find out more about our innovative approach to research and join our community of emerging leaders in novel HortiFood design using the Living Lab approach”

“Discover the results of our capacity-building project and learn how our community of researchers has collaborated to produce innovative research/food-products. Our program has empowered early stage researchers and experienced researchers to enhance their skills and work together towards common goals. Join us and contribute to a growing network of global researcher.”

“Our capacity-building project offers a unique opportunity to collaborate with a global network of researcher, share knowledge, and produce impactful research. Join us to see the results of our innovative program and learn how we are shaping the next generation of researchers. Our community of emerging leaders in novel HortiFood design using the Living Lab approach, is committed to advancing knowledge and tackling complex challenges in our rapidly changing world.”

“Our capacity-building project for research and administration management staff has successfully trained and supported a diverse group of professionals from around the world. Learn more about our innovative approaches to project administration, financial management, and reporting. Join our community of emerging leaders in research management and advance your career in this critical field.”

“HortiFoodTrends project has successfully supported universities in building their research and innovation capacity. Learn more about our innovative approaches to capacity building and the impact of our program on the participating research institutions. Join us to be part of a community of emerging leaders in novel HortiFood design using the Living Lab approach, committed to driving knowledge creation and tackling complex challenges through research and innovation.”

DC activities and tools: All, in particular: conferences, open-access publications, webinars, events organised by other EU projects/initiatives linked to the project, website, social media.

INDUSTRY & COMPANIES & INVESTORS:

Companies interested in innovative fruit and vegetables product development, sensory and consumer research, farming associations, smart farming companies, producers, technology providers. Funding bodies, private firms, VC investors.

What do we want to achieve by reaching this target group?

- Increase technology transfer and facilitate the development and implementation of innovative horticultural food products and technologies. Provide creative solutions for business through R&I collaboration, mainly related to the operation of the Living Lab. Provide access to research to responsive research adapted to citizens’ needs and context;
- Increase the awareness regarding the importance of engaging regional actors in innovation processes;
- Increase the reputation of InHort as trustworthy partners for fruitful collaboration. Engage further companies to collaborate with InHort’s researchers Increase investment in SME processing;
- Increase investment in the new innovative product that fulfilling consumers’ sensory expectations;

- Promote the project and its results;
- Engage industry, company and investors in the project activities.

Key message: creation of new opportunities for collaboration; substantial profits for investing in a new innovative product; added value of co-creation in the food sector to create innovation and increase competitiveness; high ROI by investing in the HortiFoodTrends innovative products.

Communication message:

"Join HortiFoodTrends project to build stronger partnerships between research institutions and local industry. Our program offers innovative approaches to capacity building and knowledge exchange, creating opportunities for collaboration and driving economic growth. Collaborate with a dynamic community of research and industry leaders committed to creating positive change in your local community."

Dissemination message:

"HortiFoodTrends project has successfully fostered collaboration between research institutions and local industry, building stronger partnerships and creating opportunities for knowledge exchange and innovation. Learn more about our innovative approaches to capacity building and the impact of our program on the local industry. Join us to be part of a community of emerging leaders in research and industry, committed to driving economic growth and creating positive change in your local community."

DC activities: Industry-specific events, trade publications, networking activities, Round tables, newsletter, social media.

AUTHORITIES & POLICY MAKERS

Local, regional, ministries (agriculture, economy), governmental organisations and agencies responsible for agri-food, bioeconomy, innovative production of food, food quality evaluation, innovative technologies for food preservation, InHort Liders (Director).

What do we want to achieve by reaching this target group?

- Provide the knowledge how to develop a better understanding and creating win-win partnerships between researchers, citizens, business and policymakers in the food sector in order to create innovation and increase competitiveness, thereby strengthening territorial development, also in line with the Smart Specialisation Strategy;
- Boost new policies and programmes in the food/health sector, taking into consideration project results;
- Engage authorities and policy makers in the project activities;
- Better shape InHort's policies and strategies in line with EU research policy; developing further actions to enhance InHort's international reputation and strengthen the institute's role in the local territory as a driver of innovation.

Key message: quadruple helix network of communication to enhance a sustainable development of the region; consumer-centred food innovations leading to improvement of citizens' health and reduction of the costs of treating diet-related diseases.

Communication message:

"HortiFoodTrends project aims to equip emerging leaders in academia with the skills and knowledge to address complex challenges facing society. Join us to learn about our innovative approaches to research

and innovation capacity building and how we are collaborating to drive positive change. Together, let's shape policies that make a meaningful impact on our communities."

Dissemination message:

"Our capacity-building project is creating a community of emerging leaders in academia who are equipped to address complex societal challenges. Learn more about our innovative approaches to research and innovation capacity building and how we are collaborating to drive positive change. Join us in advancing knowledge creation and shaping policies that make a difference in our communities."

DC activities and tools: All, in particular website, social media, press releases, Round Table, conference.

GENERAL PUBLIC

Citizens, consumers eager to learn more about the potential benefits of the research.

What do we want to achieve by reaching this target group?

- To communicate the potential impact of the project on daily life;
- Allow better access to high quality food products produced using up-to-date, environmentally friendly modern processing technologies;
- Encourage consumers to significantly increase their consumption of fruit and vegetables;
- Increase interest in innovative solutions and co-creation of innovative food products using modern technologies;
- Raise awareness about the role of EU funding;
- Promote the project and its results;
- Increase the reputation of InHort as trustworthy partner for fruitful collaborations;
- Engage citizens and consumers in the project activities.

Key message: healthy products for better life; added value of co-creation of innovative food products.

Communication message:

"HortiFoodTrends project aims to make a positive impact on society through research and innovation. Join us to learn about our innovative approaches to capacity building and how we are tackling complex challenges facing our communities. Together, let's create a better future for all."

Dissemination message:

"HortiFoodTrends project is dedicated to creating a positive impact on society through research and innovation. Learn more about our program and the impact it has on addressing real-world challenges. Join us in building a better future for our communities through knowledge creation and collaboration."

DC activities and tools: project website, social media, promotional materials, press releases.

MEDIA

Media including general and specialised magazines and newsletter. These play a key role in broad communication and dissemination to increase the impact of the project; influencing public opinion and attitudes.

3. DISSEMINATION STRATEGY AND PLAN

'Make knowledge and results publicly available free-of-charge'

3.1. Dissemination objectives

The dissemination activities are strategically designed to maximise the impact and reach of the project's outcomes, findings, and knowledge. The objectives of the dissemination activities are:

- create broad awareness of the HortiFoodTrends project and its objectives among the target audiences;
- facilitate the sharing of project findings, research outcomes, and innovative solutions with relevant stakeholders;
- contribute to capacity building by providing access to educational resources, training materials, and best practices, thus supporting the development of a skilled and informed workforce;
- engage various stakeholder groups for input and feedback, promoting a dynamic exchange of ideas, expertise.

3.2. Dissemination channels

3.2.1. Scientific articles

Target audience: researchers and admin staff at InHort, partner institutions and other relevant Research Centers and Universities, Scientific Community, governmental organisations and agencies responsible for agri-food, bioeconomy, innovative production of food, food quality evaluation, innovative technologies for food preservation.

Objectives:

- Disseminating novel research findings to the scientific community;
- Increasing the visibility and credibility of the project and its partners;
- Facilitating knowledge exchange and fostering potential collaborations;
- Contributing to the body of knowledge in relevant fields of study.

Publishing scientific articles is a crucial part of the dissemination strategy for HortiFoodTrends. These articles will share the project's research findings with the scientific community, contributing to the advancement of knowledge in the field of horticultural food products and consumer research.

The partners will individually and in collaboration publish and present scientific advances in technical papers (peer-reviewed) as well as in journals (peer reviewed) and specialised magazines.

To support this activity, whenever possible, project publications will be archived or linked on the HortiFoodTrends website.

Table 2: Publication on international peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings

Journal title	Web	Open Access policy
Trends in Food Science & Technology	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/trends-in-food-science-and-technology	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/trends-in-food-science-and-technology/publish/open-access-options
Food Quality and Preference	Food Quality and Preference Journal ScienceDirect.com by Elsevier	Article Authors manuscript version can be made available on authors' organisation websites When a Danish University researcher is corresponding author, there is Gold Open Access without cost to the project. Open access information - Food Quality and Preference - ISSN 0950-3293 ScienceDirect.com by Elsevier Open access Elsevier
International Journal of Gastronomy and Food Science	International Journal of Gastronomy and Food Science ScienceDirect.com by Elsevier	Same as above
Journal of Sensory Studies	Journal of Sensory Studies - Wiley Online Library	Authors manuscript version can be made available on authors' organisation websites When a Danish University researcher is corresponding author, there is Open Access without cost to the project. Journal of Sensory Studies Open Access
Food Research International	Food Research International Journal ScienceDirect.com by Elsevier	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/food-research-international/publish/open-access-options
Current Opinion in Food Science	Current Opinion in Food Science Journal ScienceDirect.com by Elsevier	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/current-opinion-in-food-science/publish/open-access-options
International Journal of Food Design	Intellect Books International Journal of Food Design	https://www.intellectbooks.com/open-access
Foods	Foods An Open Access Journal from MDPI	https://www.mdpi.com/openaccess

Whenever possible, HortiFoodTrends will exploit new opportunities given by the Open Research Europe (ORE) platform to share research outputs as early and widely as possible. See par. 3.4 Official EU Key Tools.

Project foresees:

- 4 peer-reviewed scientific articles resulting from the Programme.

According to Grant Agreement articles in peer reviewed journals will be put in Open access (see par. 3.5 Open Science).

3.2.2. Events participation

Target audience: citizens, consumers, researchers and admin staff at InHort, partner institutions and other relevant Research Centers and Universities, local, regional, ministries (agriculture, economy), governmental organisations and agencies responsible for agri-food, bioeconomy, innovative production of food, food quality evaluation, innovative technologies for food preservation, Companies interested in innovative product development, sensory and consumer research, farming associations, smart farming companies, producers, technology providers.

Objectives:

- To present and discuss the project's research findings and innovations with a wide audience;
- To build and strengthen networks with other researchers, industry professionals, policy makers, and the general public;
- To promote the HortiFoodTrends project and its objectives, encouraging participation and collaboration.

Participation in well-known and qualified international and national conferences is important in terms of disseminating the results of the project to a wider scientific audience and industrial experts.

Project promotes oral and poster presentations at scientific conferences targeting relevant domains for the project. Seminars, fairs, festivals and other major events are relevant opportunities to disseminate project results and share insights with wider communities and promote the project. By attending these events, HortiFoodTrends can effectively network with key stakeholders, and foster collaboration within the sensory/food/horticulture community. Main events relevant to the dissemination and communication strategy of the project are reported in **Table 3**.

Table 3: Events relevant to dissemination and communication strategy (Preliminary map).

Event	Date	Place	Aim	Importance for the project
16th Pangborn Sensory Science Symposium.	August 17 – 21, 2025	Philadelphia, USA;	Presentation of project progress and results from research	It is the largest and sensory and consumer science conference in the world. It brings together leading academic scientists, researchers and research scholars to exchange and share their experiences and research results on all aspects of sensory and consumer science
The International Conference on Horticulture (MDPI)	May, 27-29, 2025	Online	Presentation of project progress and results from research	It brings together leading academic scientists, researchers and research scholars to exchange and share their experiences and research results on horticulture and fruit & vegetables processing science
Eurosense	September 8-11, 2026	Oslo, Norway	Presentation of project progress	It is the largest and sensory and consumer science

			and results from research	conference in the Europe. It is regarded as the conference with the highest scientific level in the field of sensory and consumer science
Sensometrics	2026	Tbd	The Sensometric Society - Sensometrics 2024	Applied statistics research
International Conference on Food Oral Processing	May 12-15 2025	Valencia, Spain	7th International Conference on Food Oral Processing Physics, Physiology and Psychology of Eating - Home	Texture research
European Chemoreception Research Organization	September 15-18 2025	Bilbao, Spain	ISOT2024 - Home	Flavour research
The Fruit and Vegetable Industry Fair TSW	January 2026/2027	Warsaw Poland	Presentation of project progress and results from research	The largest and most important industry fair in Poland and in this part of Europe, visited by professionals and producers of fruit and vegetables, engineers, food processors and the academic community.
The Festival of Flower, Fruits and Vegetables in Skierniewice	September 2024/2025 /2026	Skierniewice, Poland	Present the project, networking	The event brings together various stakeholders related to horticulture, fruit and vegetable processing, consumer. Dissemination of project results among the community.

3.2.3. Conference organisation

Target audience: wide range of stakeholders, including horticultural researchers, specialists in sensory and consumer research, market and product- developers active in the food industry, industry representatives, academia and stakeholder representatives from other relevant projects policy makers, investors, and the general public.

Objectives:

- To present the main outcomes and innovations developed during the HortiFoodTrends project;
- To facilitate networking and knowledge exchange among stakeholders;
- To highlight the benefits and impact of the interdisciplinary collaboration established through the project;
- To make it possible for interested actors to use/exploit part of the results in their own respective work areas;
- To promote further cooperation, develop synergies, research and innovation networks.

This event is aimed at disseminating and presenting the project's research results, elaborated innovation and good practices of stakeholders' related to: innovative products and processes in the food sector. The first results in terms of new ideas for products and services, as emerged from the Living Lab/CPPO will be presented. Roadmap and avenues for future research/Scientific Strategy will be officially presented.

The event will involve a variety of participants, including stakeholders, project partners, industry experts, institutional representatives, and other interested parties. It serves as an opportunity to share the acquired knowledge, promote the project's visibility, and establish connections with other professionals or organizations that may be interested in the achieved results. Moreover, this will be the occasion to discuss next steps, such as potential practical applications of the project's outcomes or further research and related developments. Academia and stakeholder representatives from other relevant projects, R&I networks, etc. will be invited to share research, experience and good practices in the related fields to promote and identification of joint synergies and future cooperation.

3.2.4. Round Table, Summer/ Winter School, Training, Workshops organisation

Target audience: project partners, local authorities, NGOs, key experts or decision-makers, such as ministers or their deputies, as well as representatives of food production SMEs.

Objectives:

- To involve of regional actors in R&I process;
- To promote further cooperation, develop synergies, research and innovation networks;
- To make it possible for interested actors to use/exploit part of the results in their own respective work areas;
- To facilitate knowledge exchange and skill enhancement.

In order to actively engage stakeholders in innovation process, there will be organise Round Tables, Summer/Winter School, Workshops. Organisation events with face-to-face discussions have a much stronger impact and allow to establish long term relationships with future partners, customers or providers and to learn insightful information about the field.

Representants of the quadruple helix network will be invited to take part in the Round Table. During the meeting there will be presented the project research results and will cover topics essential for enhancing knowledge transfer of novel HortiFood designed in the Living-Lab formula, as well as possible channels and forms of dialogue of potential life cycle scenarios for the implemented innovations.

In addition, case studies with consumers will be conducted to explore their level of acceptance of new products. Expert interviews will be conducted on decisions of human, social, material aspects of responsible innovation. The results will be taken into account in the development of the DCE and the preparation of activities to raise public awareness of new foods with health-promoting properties.

By organization of Summer/ Winter School, Training, participants will have the opportunity to learn from leading experts, engage in discussions, and explore collaboration opportunities in the evolving field. In order to disseminate the knowledge and good practices gained during the visits to the project partners, 2 workshops per year will be organised for the InHort community. During the workshops, administrators and researchers will transfer the acquired knowledge.

3.3. Synergies with relevant existing networks/projects

In order to increase the visibility of the project in the stakeholder community, HortiFoodTrends will establish links, interaction and synergies with European networks, societies, partnerships, founded project working on same topic that HortiFoodTrends;, other relevant stakeholders e.g. (Ministries, Operational Groups working on relevant topics).

This could take the form of:

- joint dissemination (disseminating materials within their organization), participation and co-organization of events, social media support - mutual promotion of news;
- exchange knowledge, experience, and best practices.

Projects under the same call often share goals and are aimed at similar audiences. By connecting and clustering with likeminded beneficiaries — for example, by following their account, retweeting or replying to their posts or tagging them — you can attract each other’s followers and fans, enlarging your community of interested individuals and organisations.

Table 4: List of other projects, initiatives and international societies for project dissemination

Other projects, initiatives, societies	Relevance for the project
SEASONED Project (GA: 101079003)	A Widera project with similar purpose as HortiFoodTrends. To strengthen communication about the importance of sensory research for consumers in Poland and other European countries
European Sensory Network	To strengthen communication about the importance of sensory research for consumers
European Sensory Science Society	
Section of Food Sensory Analyses of the Polish Food Technologists' Society	
EIT Food	Join the world’s largest and most dynamic food innovation community to get know tools and ways for create innovative berry products.

3.4. Official EU Key Tools

HortiFoodTrends will communicate through the European Commission’s channels. Project consortium is part of the Community Research and Development Information Service ([CORDIS](#)). It is not only a structured public repository of all project information held by the European Commission, but also it provides News and Events service.

The most important findings of the project will be suggested to the editors of [Horizon Magazine](#). The magazine presents the latest news and features about science and innovative research projects funded by the EU.

The following EU tools will also be considered by partners:

- [Open Research Europe platform](#): An open access, publishing platform for scientific papers for Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe beneficiaries, including an open peer review and article revision.
- [Horizon Results platform](#): A platform for showcasing research results, finding collaboration opportunities and getting inspired by the results of others. It is a place where beneficiaries can upload and promote the Key Exploitable Results (KER) of their projects, and can also be used as a matchmaking tool, making it easier to meet people interested in their results.

- **Horizon Results Booster:** Free consulting services including a portfolio dissemination and exploitation strategy, business plan development and go-to-market support.
- **Innovation radar:** An initiative that identifies high-potential innovations, based on a data-driven methodology, and assists EU-funded researchers and innovators in reaching the market with their innovation.

3.5. Open Science

The Data Management Plan (D7.2 released in M6) gives detailed instructions on how to manage and store research data and indicates the cases in which research data can be made publicly available.

3.6. Dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Table 5: Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) related to dissemination activities

Action	KPIs	Target
Scientific articles	No of peer-reviewed scientific articles resulting from the Programme	4
	% of articles shared on ResearchGate, Web of Science	100%
	No of citations per year	3
	No of full-text views per year	1000
	No of abstract views per year	1500
	KPI 1: No of publications in peer-reviewed journals published by InHort's research departments engaged into project; per year	30
	KPI 8: No of publications in peer-reviewed journals submitted by the project consortium	5
	KPI 16: No of articles published by InHort's research departments engaged into project in open access	8
	KPI 17: No of citation at the end of the project	150
Event participation	No of conferences, seminars, fairs, festivals per year	5
	KPI 19: No of presentations at conferences including oral presentations and posters made by InHort's scientific staff	30
Conference organization	No of organized conference	1
	No of participants	150
	No outstanding scientists invited to the conference to give a lecture	6
	KPI 22: No of active participants in the organised conference	50
	KPI 2: No of invited speakers to give lectures at HortiFoodTrends Conference	8
Round Table	KPI 7: 1 network, 4 partners	1
	No of participants	Not defined
Summer/ Winter School, Training, Workshops organisation	No of workshops per year	2
	KPI 3: No of scientists from InHort visiting Partners' Institutions	10
	KPI 4: No of visits of scientists from Partners' institutions	14
	KPI 20: No of scientists from Partners' institutions visiting InHort	10
	KPI 21: No of researchers (including young) engaged in the project	20 (10 ESR)
	KPI 23: No of upskilled researchers involved in the Project	34
	KPI 26: Organized thematic courses (workshops/training/ winter school)	6
	KPI 27: No of researchers participating in the courses	50
	KPI 28: No of internships (2-week travels)	6
KPI 29: No of researchers participating in the internships	6	

KPI 30: No of study visits (up to 1-week travel)	12
KPI 31: No of scientists going to partners for study visits	6
KPI 32: No of administrative staff going to partners for study visits	4
KPI 35: No of upskilled management and administrative staff	7

4. COMMUNICATION STRATEGY AND PLAN

'Inform, promote and communicate activities and results'

4.1. Communication objectives

The overall objective of the communication activities is to broadly inform targeted audiences about the project. Therefore, it is necessary to build and maintain an effective communication within the project and to ensure large spreading of the project results to the industry community, the scientific community, policy makers and the general public.

The aims of communication activities are:

- raise public awareness and ensure maximum visibility of the project's key facts, objectives, activities, and findings, its implications for citizens and society;
- enhance acceptance and demand for new foods with health-promoting properties;
- announce and promote HortiFoodTrends events;
- engage stakeholders in the project activities;
- support the dissemination objectives;
- to increase the reputation of InHort among stakeholders as trustworthy partners for fruitful collaborations.

4.2. Communication tools and channels

The Communication activity will be focused on the use of different tools to reach the largest audience possible, talking to them in a clear and easy language to translate technical information into more affordable and easier to understand messages.

4.2.1. Project Website

Target audience: citizens, consumers, researchers and admin staff at InHort, partner institutions and other relevant Research Centers and Universities, local, regional, ministries (agriculture, economy), governmental organisations and agencies responsible for agri-food, bioeconomy, innovative production of food, food quality evaluation, innovative technologies for food preservation, companies interested in innovative product development, sensory and consumer research, farming associations, smart farming companies, producers, technology providers.

Objectives:

- to raise awareness of the project activities, objectives and results;
- to increase the visibility of the project within the European research and industry communities and European stakeholders.

The main communication tool of the HortiFoodTrends project is the project website - www.hortifoodtrends.eu. The purpose of the website is to gather all information about project concept, news, events and results during the entire duration of the project and beyond. The website will remain active for at least 5 years after the end of the project.

It includes contact points for the people involved in the project, as well as a list of project partners. The website is linked to partners' websites and vice versa. Furthermore, the website will be mentioned in all dissemination and communication tools, such as presentations, posters, brochures, and invitations for events.

The website consists of the following sections:

- **ABOUT** - describes the project's objectives, work-packages, and consortium members. Offers access to project-related publications, public deliverables, research papers, reports, and other valuable content, enriching the audience's knowledge and understanding of the project's field.
- **COMMUNICATIONS** - provides regular updates on project progress, recent achievements, upcoming events, and activities, fostering engagement and promoting awareness.
- **CONTACT** - facilitates communication for queries, collaboration opportunities and feedback, ensuring stakeholders can easily interact with the project team.
- **MEDIA** - provides files to download e.g. logotypes, press releases.
- **NEWSLETTER** – includes Newsletter subscription form.
- **SOCIAL MEDIA BUTTONS** – the project website is linked to project's profiles on social media (Facebook, LinkedIn, X Platform).

While InHort is in charge of updating the content of the website, all partners are encouraged to contribute items related to the subject, including news, local events and relevant information, and in particular project updates, videos, images, and news related to project outputs. The website will be updated regularly. Improvements to the design and management of the website will be made on a regular basis.

4.2.2. Social Media channels

Target audience: citizens, consumers, researchers and admin staff at InHort, partner institutions and other relevant Research Centers and Universities, local, regional, ministries (agriculture, economy), governmental organisations and agencies responsible for agri-food, bioeconomy, innovative production of food, food quality evaluation, innovative technologies for food preservation, companies interested in innovative product development, sensory and consumer research, farming associations, smart farming companies, producers, technology providers.

Objectives:

- To raise awareness of the HortiFoodTrends project and its objectives;
- To engage with a wide range of stakeholders including researchers, industry professionals, policy makers and the general public;
- To disseminate project results, updates and information on events and seminars;
- To foster an online community around the project and encourage interaction and discussion.

Social media channels, especially LinkedIn, Facebook and Twitter, are great tools both for communicating the project main messages and activity as well as for the dissemination of project results. The project has three main social media channels:

- [LinkedIn](#)

- [Facebook](#)
- [X](#)

The choice of social network was driven by the diversity of its users.

LinkedIn is a social platform fully oriented towards professional purposes. It is a place to network and share experiences with business audiences and other scientists. It is one of the platforms with the largest number of accounts for EU-funded projects and EU institutions.

Facebook brings together a cross-section of society, from older people to Generation Z and Millennials¹. Users of this platform share their content with friends and interact with friends, but also browse interesting thematic profiles and share their content on their profiles². Facebook's broad cross-section of users allows it to reach end consumers. The content published on the HortiFoodTrends project profile includes: coverage of project events, announcements of events organised by project implementers and content on topics related to healthy food production.

Platform X is mainly associated with politicians and content related to politics and citizenship. It is the place to reach authorities and policy makers as well as those involved in the food industry. The platform offers the opportunity to quickly share news and events and reach a global audience³.

Recommended Social Media Plan

In order to benefit from project social media channels them it is necessary to build a solid content strategy and to commit the partners to implement the plan.

Partners will consider the following good practices when preparing content for social media:

- Describe topic of the publication or write the publication itself. Put attention to: clear and comprehensible communication, short sentences, vocabulary suitable for target audience, aspects relevant to the target audience. Character limit: 280 for X, almost unlimited for Facebook and 3000 for LinkedIn.
- Include a link to relevant content: HortiFoodTrends website, partner webpages, external webpages, industry reports, upcoming events or conferences, social media profiles, educational videos, blog articles, press releases or any other online resource that provides additional value and insight on the topic.
- Indicate where the publication will attach an image/video or not. Image and media are important in all social platforms, but more so in Facebook.
- Include the hastags. Using a hashtag makes the keyword or phrase in the post searchable. This makes it easier for users to locate specific content or topics. Always use : #HortiFoodTrendsEU and other relevant e.g.: #HorizoneEU, #ReserchImpactEU, #EUInnovation
- Include mentions to other accounts to increase the reach of the post. IMPORTANT: names in LinkedIn, Facebook and X, usually are different, look for the user name for the organisation/person you wish to tag for each platform. **Tag project partners, REA, the national NCPs social accounts** were relevant. The Project Social Media accounts will highly benefit from the support of these bigger institutions with existing online connections and a stronger follower base.

¹ <https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/fact-sheet/social-media/>

² <https://www.oberlo.com/statistics/why-do-people-use-facebook>

³ <https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/2024/06/12/how-x-users-view-experience-the-platform/>

- [@REA_research](#) [@EUgreenresearch](#) [@HorizonEU](#)
- [@European Research Executive Agency](#)
[@EU Science, Research and Innovation](#)
- [@EU Science and Innovation](#)
- [@EU_Science](#)
- [@EC_REA](#)
- [European Research Executive Agency](#)

Table 6: Partners’ social accounts

InHort	UCPH	GROUPE ESA	LYFE
Facebook	Facebook	Facebook	Facebook
LinkedIn	LinkedIn	LinkedIn	LinkedIn
YouTube	YouTube	YouTube	Instagram
	Instagram	Instagram	TikTok
	X	X	
		TikTok	

The recommended content strategy for the social media channel considers:

- Series of post with different basic messages of the project with the purpose to building awareness on the goals of HortiFoodTrends and on the problems it seeks to solve.
- Once awareness is built, it is possible to start communicating the activity and results of the project. The targeted audience (depending on the social media channel) will be more receptive and understand better the materials HortiFoodTrends is providing and talking about.
- The “Basic Messages” posts can be used again throughout the project. In order to not be repetitive, it is recommended to pay attention to the programming (making sure that the same message was not posted too soon before) and to make small updates in the messages or the images occasionally.
- The Basic Messages, together with posts related to the activity of the project partners and the dissemination of the results of the project, will build a solid content strategy.

4.2.3. Project Newsletter and Press Releases

Target audience citizens, consumers, researchers and admin staff at InHort, partner institutions and other relevant Research Centers and Universities, local, regional, ministries (agriculture, economy), governmental organisations and agencies responsible for agri-food, bioeconomy, innovative production of food, food quality evaluation, innovative technologies for food preservation, companies interested in innovative product development, sensory and consumer research, farming associations, smart farming companies, producers, technology providers.

Objectives:

- To provide regular updates on the project's activities, achievements, and upcoming events;

- To maintain engagement with stakeholders and keep them informed about the project's progress. Highlight significant innovations and research findings;
- To promote participation in project-related events and activities;
- Promote collaboration opportunities and attract potential partners and investors.

Newsletters will be distributed on a regular basis (4 newsletters/year) to disseminate the project’s progress, milestones and key results. This tool will also be used for promoting the public events organized within the project. The first newsletter is planned to be sent on M7. The newsletter will be prepared in English. Translations into the national languages of the partners will be considered.

These newsletters will be sent proactively to existing and further enlarged mailing list of recipients from local government, academia, business, NGOs and other relevant stakeholders, as well as to all other project partners' dissemination channels (e.g. via link on social media). The another channel for spreading the newsletter will be the HortiFoodTrends website by “Newsletter subscription form”.

Recommended Newsletter Plan

The Newsletters must contain meaningful content for professionals as well as assisting in promoting the HortiFoodTrends project. The newsletter is less focused on experts in the field but more focused on raising public awareness of new foods with health-promoting properties.

Partners will consider the following editorial principles and structure recommendations for newsletter content:

The content should be:

- Short
- Non-technical
- Engaging
- Set within a real world context
- Eye-catching
- Enjoyable to read
- Easy to read on screen as mail chimp produced HTML

The suggested structure of the newsletter is shown in the **Table 7. Table 7: Newsletter structure**

Table 7: Newsletter structure

<p>Header:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project title and logo • EU Logo and disclaimer • Newsletter theme/topic title
<p>Body:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction from the coordinator or a work package leader • Feature news article (see schedule in <i>Table 8</i>) • Invitation to project events (optional) • Call-to-Action (CTA): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Links to further news stories on the website (list) – Latest project publications (list) – Link to website and social media channels

Footer:

- Social sharing
- Contact details (for project)
- Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.
- Legal information about GDPR and the possibility of unsubscribe

The planning of the newsletters and their planned theme can be found in **Table 8**.

Table 8: Newsletter planning and e.g. themes

No.	Month	Theme
1	M7	The Importance of International Collaboration in Research and Product Development. Project presentation and roles of the partners involved in HortiFoodTrends (InHort).
2	M9	Nutrition Tips: fruits and vegetables in Your Daily Diet (InHort).
3	M11	Sensory evaluation - why it is important in assessing product quality (ESA).
4	M13	Consumer research: Context effects in meal appreciation and real-life testing solutions for consumer studies (LYFE).
5	M15	Industry Event Highlights & Projects Promoting Healthy Diets (InHort).
6	M18	Health-promoting value of berries – the importance of bioactive compounds (InHort).
7	M21	An intensive training program on sensory evaluation and consumers oriented method (ESA).
8	M24	Consumer research – Elaboration of the determinants of product choices and acceptance in relation to innovative fruit-based products (UCPH).
9	M27	Consumer research : Involving chefs and end-users in product design and orientation (LYFE).
10	M30	Sensory evaluation in the innovation process – methods and strategies to evaluate product prototypes at all stages from concept to launching of product (UCPH).
11	M33	The Importance of International Collaboration in Research and Product Development (InHort).
12	M36	Living-Lab and Co-Creation – practical approaches to engaging stakeholders in innovation development (InHort).

Press releases will be sent to appropriate media outlets (trade press, journals, web portals) to ensure that industry, civil society organisations, policy-making authorities, and the wider community are aware of the project, its objectives and, later in the project - its outcomes.

12 pieces of articles, press releases and news are initially foreseen to be published throughout the project. Each press release will carry a key message about the project’s work, with the aim of generating interest about the project’s activities.

The strategy is intended to ensure that there is publicity and media coverage at local, regional and European levels. Project partners have several existing channels and networks for disseminating news which will ensure a broad awareness of the project across the spectrum of relevant European stakeholders.

The content of the press releases will be developed in Polish and if relevant – in English and will be sent to other beneficiaries. Beneficiaries will have to translate the press releases in their national languages and may personalise them according to their needs and specific features. Translated and personalised press releases will be sent to relevant local media.

4.2.4. Promotion materials

Target audience: local, regional, ministries (agriculture, economy), governmental organisations and agencies responsible for agri-food, bioeconomy, innovative production of food, food quality evaluation, innovative technologies for food preservation, companies interested in innovative product development, sensory and consumer research, farming associations, smart farming companies, producers, technology providers, funding bodies, private firms, VC investors.

Objectives:

- To visually represent the HortiFoodTrends project and its key messages;
- To provide easily accessible and understandable information about the project;
- To attract and engage stakeholders and potential collaborators;
- To promote project events, results and opportunities.

To establish the project’s visual identity and to attract the target group’s attention promotional materials will be distributed during the HortiFoodTrends events and activities and continuously updated. All materials inform about the HortiFoodTrends project and its objectives. They contain contacts for feedback and further information.

These materials will be distributed both digitally and in print, maximizing reach and effectiveness in raising awareness and fostering active engagement with the project's target groups. The produced material should be graphically consistent and aligned with HortiFoodTrends graphical guidelines.

The designs and visuals of the promotional materials are attached to the DCE Plan (see Annex 1).

4.3. Communication Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Table 9: Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) related to communication activities

Action	KPIs	Target
Project website	Visit to website	30 000
	Countries from which visitors come	20
Social media - Facebook	No of followers	300
Social media - LinkedIn	No of followers	100
Social media - X	No of followers	300
	No of tweets per month	3
Project newsletters	No of newsletters per year	4
	No of recipients	1 000
Press releases	No of press releases per year	4
Promotional material	No of e-material distributed to people at events	500

4.4. Visual Identity

The visual identity of the HortiFoodTrends project is essential to ensure recognition, consistency, and professional representation across all communication materials. It can also help to build brand recognition and trust among stakeholders.

The primary logo of HortiFoodTrends consists of a stylized plant symbol with green and blue elements and a magenta dot, accompanied by the project name in a modern, legible font. This logo should be used in its original form to maintain brand integrity.

Colour Palette:

- Green: #32A852
- Blue: #004F9F
- Magenta: #CC0066

These colours are integral to the HortiFoodTrends identity and should be used consistently across all materials.

The use of a logo is subject to the following rules:

- Digital Use: The logo should be used in digital formats such as the project website, social media, newsletters, and digital publications. Ensure the logo is clear and legible on all digital platforms.
- Print Use: For printed materials like posters, leaflets, flyers, and conference materials, the logo should be printed in high resolution. It is crucial to maintain the correct colour codes for consistency.
- Backgrounds: The logo should preferably be placed on a white or light background to ensure maximum visibility and contrast. Avoid using the logo on dark or cluttered backgrounds.
- Clear Space: Maintain a clear space around the logo equal to the height of the magenta dot to ensure it stands out and is not crowded by other elements.

The logo is used to mark project documentation, promotional materials and the website and social media accounts.

By following these common graphic identity guidelines, the HortiFoodTrends project will establish a strong and recognisable graphic identity to support its communication and dissemination efforts.

4.5. Funding Statements

When communicating and disseminating with external stakeholders, partners will ensure to acknowledge the EU support and display the European flag (emblem) as stated in article 17 of the Grant Agreement.

The EU flag cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands, or text. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g., leading or partner institution), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos. All allowed flag options with the funding statement can be downloaded from the following link:

https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en

Together with the EU flag **the funding statement** “Funded by the European Union” will be included in all official project documents.

Additionally, the statement “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101159293. (HortiFoodTrends).” will be used where appropriate.

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the project must use factually accurate information and it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

The EU flag and funding statement must be displayed in a way that is easily visible for the public and with sufficient prominence. EU funding must moreover be acknowledged in all types of public outputs (*including patent applications, EU standardisation of results*), media contacts and other public statements.

4.6. European General Data Protection Regulations

A description of the strategy to ensure the protection of the results and the data generated is covered in the Consortium Agreement (CA) Chapter 9 of CA *Access Rights* collects the principles that the partners will follow concerning the data protection strategy. More information on the HortiFoodTrends data protection strategy is also presented in the Data Management Plan (DMP).

5. EXPLOITATION STRATEGY AND PLAN

‘Make concrete use of results for commercial, societal and political purposes’

5.1. Obligation and definitions

Beneficiaries receiving EU funding must – **up to four years after the end of the action** – use their best efforts to **exploit** their **results** directly or to have them exploited indirectly by another entity, in particular through licensing or transfer

If, despite a beneficiary’s best efforts, the results are not exploited within one year after the end of the action, the beneficiaries must (unless otherwise agreed in writing with the granting authority) use the **Horizon Results Platform** to find interested parties to exploit the results (see Annex 5 of GA).

Beneficiaries have an obligation to **define and list the expected key results that might be exploited** (including their: description, ownership status – basis for Research Ownership List to be included in the final report, sector of application, protection measures) and their **strategy for exploitation and dissemination**.

(see: Annex 5 of GA, [Article 39: Exploitation and dissemination](#)).

Exploitation is defined as the utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

Results are defined as any (tangible or intangible) output of the action such as data, knowledge, or information – whatever its form or nature, whether it can be protected or not – that is generated in the action, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights.

A **Key Exploitable Result** is an identified interesting result which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be "exploited" – meaning to make use and derive benefits- downstream of the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research, or education.

5.2. Potential exploitation routes

Project results will be exploited by the project partners according to the nature of each of the outcome. Below is a list outlining where exploitation may take place, taking into account intellectual property rights issues.

- **Partnerships:** Collaborating with organisation, industry partners to integrate the project's results into existing products or services.
- **Commercialization:** Selling project’s technologies or services developed through the project to businesses or consumers (e.g. laboratory analysis and research project in CPPO adopted Living Lab approach).
- **Patenting** new technologies on EU level.
- **Licensing:** Granting other companies or organizations the right to use the project's intellectual property in exchange for royalties and/or fees.
- **Spin-offs:** Creating new startup companies based on technologies or innovations developed during the project (e.g. by ESR of HortiFoodTrends project).
- **Technology transfer:** Transferring knowledge and technology developed in the project to other industries or applications.

- **Policy impact:** Informing and influencing policy decisions based on the project's findings and recommendations.
- **Capacity building:** Training programs or workshops to share expertise and knowledge gained from the project with relevant stakeholders.
- **Open-source dissemination:** Making project results freely available to the public for further development and use (New applied or follow-up research, when the results are intended to be engaged in new research proposals and activities).
- **Education and outreach:** Developing educational materials or outreach programs to raise awareness and disseminate project findings to wider audiences. Integrations of PhD thesis.

The exploitation strategy covers three key phases, each essential for maximizing the impact of the project results (with commercial and non-commercial potential) and ensuring successful implementation.

- I. Monitoring and mapping – Identification and description of KERs.
- II. Positioning – IPR assessment and analysis of exploitation options.
- III. Exploiting – Elaboration of exploitation plans.

5.3. The context of project activities that generate results

The Work Packages **WP1**, **WP2**, **WP3** aim to enhance the development and build the capacity of InHort staff (Early-Stage Researchers, Experienced Researchers and Admin Staff). The **WP1** is focused on increasing competence of InHort scientific team, connected with sensory and consumer research methodology. **WP2** is devoted to increasing knowledge on Living Lab approach by involving ESR in research programme realized at Laboratories of more advanced Partners. Experience gathered during internship or STMS will give opportunity to better understand the idea of novel food designing or methods of communication with end-user. **WP3** will provide the necessary knowledge and tools to increase research performance indicators, to increase capacity of InHort to attract and manage EU grants and to enhance general knowledge about innovation and technology transfer in the context of planning and managing R&D projects.

The skills and knowledge transferred from Advanced Partner into InHort (**WP1**, **WP2**, **WP3**), will be immediately exploited in the Work Package **WP4**. This applies to both current knowledge in the field of methodology and skills in conducting sensory and consumer research (**WP1**), acquired experience in the Living Lab approach in designing innovative food products (**WP2**), and the effects of summer/winter school focused on skills in writing high-quality scientific papers (**WP3**), to be able to effectively publishing results obtained during the Joint Exploratory Research.

In **WP4** the Partners will perform preparation and implementation of a full cycle of the process of creation an innovative, consumer-oriented HortiFood products, taking into account the Living Lab approach. The ambition of this **WP4** is that the innovative products being developed here are to be distinguished by high nutritional and antioxidant quality and sensory attractiveness, able to contributing to the increase in the consumption of fruit and vegetables. The raw material for the innovative HortiFood products will be species belonging to the 'super fruit' group.

The summary of the implementation of joint tasks related to the end-user expectations, preferences & behaviors and willingness to invest in potential of HortiFood innovative products will be presented during an international Round Table meeting with representants a Quadruple Helix. The conclusions of the joint research in the form of original scientific articles will become an input for establishing InHort scientific strategy including the Living Lab approach (**WP5**), that will integrate research and innovation processes in line with consumers' and entrepreneurs' needs. Thus, it will support the commercialisation of new products. The elaborated strategy for novel HortiFood product creation will not only become a tool to

support a sustainable network with advanced partners, but will also have the potential to become a tool to support both people's wellbeing and the potential of the agri-food sector.

The objective of **WP6** is to disseminate the results achieved in the project. The aim is to keep continuous contact with all involved stakeholders as well as to develop a strong international network and reputation. This WP will implement a series of DCE measures designed to maximize the outreach of project results and network activities, to maximize the input from the community, and to train and transfer knowledge to practitioners enhancing their professional development. The Work Package **WP7** will be entirely devoted to project management and coordination.

The result of these activities will be:

- **Highly qualified personnel of InHort** (both scientific and admin), that creates opportunities for all partners in the consortium. InHort staff will required the essential skills to increase performance indicators, provide outputs for the achieved research, research management capacity and administrative skills. This will contribute to InHort's visibility and reputation, as well as improving its ability to access funding and resources.
- **New InHort competencies** to carry out work in the consumer-oriented formula, and in particular using the Living-Lab approach. It is expected to provide impact beyond the project by increasing technology transfer and facilitating the development and implementation of innovative horticultural food products and technologies, making them more attractive to industry stakeholders.
- The first **Living Lab approach** for research related to the agri-food sector involving civil society and end-users in the co-creation and sensory and consumer testing of innovative horticultural food products in Poland. Adaptation of the CPPO to fulfil its function in line with the Living Lab approach. CPPO will conduct consumer and industry driven projects in accordance with the procedures and standards developed by all consortium partners.
The R&I collaboration, mainly related to the functioning of Living Lab, will provide creative solutions for business. The intersectoral collaboration will implement the concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) due to which enterprises will take into account relations with stakeholders, social interests, sustainability and environment protection in their strategy. The economic impact will be related to providing services to business community and intensification of future research activity at InHort.
- **Strategy for development end-user oriented novel HortiFood products with potential to increase fruit and vegetable consumption.** The main outcome of this task is the deliverable 5.3 – Scientific Strategy including the Living Lab approach and Action Plan and since it is a confidential deliverable so it will not be publicly available. The exploitable outcome of this task will be the set of recommendations and feedback that the networks of food technologists (InHort) and specialists in the field of consumer sciences (UCPH, GROUPE ESA, LYFE) involved in this task will receive. These will include optimising the positioning of the R&D offering, highlighting ways to overcome any problems identified by the Investor and, in particular, creating a roadmap for effective communication with end users. The networks will use the recommendations to promote the sustainability (mainly, the economic one) of the networks in the long term. These, in turn, will impact InHort's excellence in the field of novel food products development, considering the needs of the end-user for creating health-promoting novel foods. It is expected to become a tool fostering human well-being and agri-food sector capacity.

- **Importance of super berries.** Raising awareness of the beneficial effects of consuming berries rich in anthocyanins like chokeberry, blueberry or Saskatoon berry which retain a special position among the 'super fruit' group. It is expected that the Project will enable the popularization of these super fruits not only among the Polish community but also among residents of other European countries.
- **New products, services or technology.** The acquisition of new competencies by InHort staff and the adaptation of the CPPO to fulfil its function according to the Living Lab approach will facilitate the development and implementation of innovative horticultural food products and technologies. The results of Join Exploratory Research will be developing exemplary innovative HortiFood products with outstanding pro-health properties. The industry and companies will receive possibilities to expand their portfolio with innovative, nutritionally and sensory valuable products. It is estimated that fulfilling consumers' sensory expectations may increase buying products of 5-10%. Thus business can expected obtaining significant returns on their investment in the new innovative product, what will have an impact on increasing economic growth. Citizens and consumers will have better access to high-quality food products produced using current, environmentally friendly modern processing technologies. In the long term, it is expected that the project may affect the increase of fruit and vegetables consumption what considered the main way to improve citizens' health and reduce the costs of treating diet-related diseases.
- **Collaborative projects.** Over the course of the project, the consortium intends to develop several collaborative project proposals, as well as carry out Join Exploratory Research within WP4. Collaborative projects offer several opportunities for HortiFoodTrends partners to exploit the outcomes and benefits of the project. One way is through knowledge transfer and sharing of expertise, where consortium members can leverage the skills and knowledge of the other organizations involved in the project. This can lead to the development of new ideas and innovations that can benefit each partner's mission and objectives. Another way is through resource sharing, where each partners can share their resources, including staff, equipment, and facilities, to achieve the project's goals and widen its reach. This can reduce costs and increase efficiency in project implementation. Collaborative projects can also provide networking opportunities for HortiFoodTrends partners to establish new partnerships and collaborations. By working together on a project, partners can build trust and strengthen their relationships, which can lead to further collaborations and partnerships in the future. In addition, collaborative projects can help InHort to increase its visibility and reputation, as well as improve InHort staff ability to access funding and resources. By demonstrating their ability to work collaboratively, partners can showcase their capacity for teamwork and innovation, which can be attractive to funders and other stakeholders.
- **International Research Management Office** at InHort. The activation of a dedicated unit within the Projects Office to support project application, management and reporting, and the enhancement of research management capacity and administrative skills of InHort staff will translate into effective application for EU project funding.
- **Training materials.** Jointly developed training materials can be exploited by the partners in several ways. First, these training materials can be disseminated widely to other organizations in the same sector to share knowledge and best practices. This can be achieved through open-access online platforms, workshops or training sessions, conferences or webinars. The partners can also use these materials to train their employees, enhancing their skills and knowledge base.

- **Publications, Poster, Presentations, Data.** HortiFoodTrends project will contribute to specific scientific advances, across and within disciplines of science of agriculture and horticulture as well as nutrition and food technology, including the use of models, algorithms and other state-of-art techniques in the sensory evaluation of food products and consumer research. These can be exploited in further research activities and publications with insightful results.
- **Stakeholder engagement events.** It is planned to organise roundtables, a final conference and case studies within the project involving external stakeholders. These events can be exploited by the partners in various ways. Networking opportunities: events offer a platform for different organizations to connect and build relationships. Attendees can exchange ideas, discuss challenges, and identify areas of collaboration. Partners can use these opportunities to build partnerships, share resources, and develop joint initiatives. Learning from each other, sharing best practices and gaining new insights will be helpful in designing novel food consumer-oriented in the Living-Lab formula.
- **Roadmaps, report** – Authorities and Policy Makers will benefit from obtaining the knowledge (D5.3) how to develop a better understanding and creating win-win partnerships between researchers, citizens, business and policymakers. Impact – revision or creation of a new directive or regulations.

5.4. Exploitable results

In this section presents Key Exploitable Results (KER) that have been already identified by partners. During project every partner will be engaged and periodically consulted for the identification of exploitable results. This section will be updated for each beneficiary during subsequent updates of DCE Plan.

Table 10: List of exploitable results

KER (Exploitation Lead)	Target audience	Exploitation route	Protection strategy	Timeframe
Innovative HortiFood products with outstanding pro-health properties (InHort)	Consumers Industry and companies	Commercial: These will be further detailed.	Patent, protected know-how	After obtaining protection
Publications based on project results	Scientific community, ESR	international scientific journals, popular science publications	open access	From completion
Developing a Living Lab approach in agri-food sector	fruit and vegetable growers food producers	new services and commercial products	n/a	Continuous
Strategy	Research community within the consortium	Organized joint R&D activity with regional relevance	Copyright	Continuous
Training materials	Research community within the consortium	To be included in InHort knowledge base and used internally, online availability	Copyright	From completion
Research report	Policymakers, local industry	Uptake by local government in future policymaking.	n/a	End of the project&beyond

The exact ways in which the HortiFoodTrends products (KER no. 1) will be exploited are yet to be concluded, but some initial strategies on that matter have been investigated by the consortium. The details of ownership and exploitation routes will be re-evaluated as the technologies become more mature.

At a later point, once the technologies have matured, an opportunity will be given to evaluate the real exploitation potential of the results of the project, as well as the capacity and interest to gain a commercial advantage. The distribution of protection costs along with the management and operational issues concerning the results, as well as the strategy for the utilization and commercialization of the results and the products will be analysed at a later stage.

5.5. Exploitation activities

Work Package 4 has the character of Joint Experimental Research, within which the Partners will perform preparation and implementation of a full cycle of the process of creation of innovative, consumer-oriented HortiFood products, taking into account the Living Lab approach. The results of the joint research in WP4 will become the main elements of exploitation activities.

- **Technological Watch and selection of knowledge outputs.** First step of analysis of experimental results will be focused on evaluation of their significance with respect to contemporary science and selection of results and knowledge with importance beyond current state of the art. Consortium should stay updated about the latest developments, follow market trends, and plan the possible publication or patenting of project results.
Besides choosing the most valuable scientific contributions for dissemination through publications in scientific journals and presentation at international conferences, analysis of project results and obtained knowledge will also include selection of those with possible impact on stakeholders (potential industrial partners and general public) and potential exploitation beyond project timeline.
- **Selection of key exploitable results.** Among previously formed collection of knowledge outputs of HortiFoodTrends those data evaluated as suitable for designing innovations in field of novel HortiFood products development, considering the needs of the end-users with using the Living Lab approach will be primarily nominated as potential KERs. Selection will be further refined by choosing those with high potential for market uptake and most easily transferable by the project. General Assembly will reach decision, hence all partners will assess the knowledge created and give their opinions on the potential KERs.
To support the exploitation management, the **Exploitation Register** will be set up. This tool will be used to monitor the progress of innovations and individual exploitation plans starting from the already identified KERs and to explore new possibilities for innovation.
- **Intellectual Property Rights Management.** In accordance with Article 16 of GA relevant measures will be taken on Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) protection and management. All the results coming from research stage of the project will be carefully evaluated in terms of possible IP protection. In case of potential patentable results, the novelty analysis will be conducted using available patent databases and with support of patent attorney. The decision on filling any patent application will be discussed by all the partners involved in the inventions, taking into account the commercial potential. To mitigate possibility of internal disagreements, involved partners will sign separate agreements on Joint patent ownership and commercialization rules. Those will encompass standard issues concerning compliance with internal IPR regulations of each partner, patent shares, range and geographical scope of protection, parties responsible for patent process and commercialization strategy, distribution of costs and so on. In case of identification of non-patentable research results with commercial potential (like know-how) the partners will define

the strategy of their utilization and protection. In those cases the consortium will form rules concerning protection of key findings including confidentiality rules and rules of interacting with potential commercial partners. The IPR protection strategy will take into account the scope of the publications and all the other IP disclosures to ensure that no patentable results will be made public before launching patent process, while providing maximum dissemination and communication of the project results.

- **Getting feedback from target audience.** The feedback of wider audience is necessity for confirmation of selection of KERs. Exploring the level of acceptance of new products provides the opportunity to take precise actions aimed at the rational use of raw material resources, infrastructure, and innovative pro-environmental methods. Feedback will be provided during various planned communication and dissemination activities, such as Round Table discussion, seminars, participation in international business fairs and commercial exhibitions, face-to-face meetings with stakeholders. During Round Table principle barriers to the adaptation of innovations like policy-related bottlenecks, financial, research, societal, geographical obstacles will be considered. All this information will help to select the most promising innovations for future applications and provide information on needed improvements. This information will be also used for identification of commercial partners.
- **Market Analysis:** Once the key exploitable results have been defined, a market analysis will be carried out to assess the potential of each.
- **Business Model:** the Business Model Canvas or/and the Value Proposition Canvas will be used to design a business model for a specific result. Target users will be defined, the potential sales strategies (direct sales, licensing, joint venture, spin out...), will be identified and the requirements for further technology development/scale-up to support market entry will be assessed.

Table 11: Exploitation Register - template

Name of the result Lead partner(s) Result type	Lead (point of reference) partner for the result <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCI: Scientific discovery, model, theory (...) • PROD: Product (new or improved) • SERV: Service (new or improved) • PROC: Industrial process (new or improved) • BUS: Business model (new or improved) • DSG: Design (new or improved) • METH: Method, material, technology, design (new or improved) • PO: Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy • EVNT: Event (conference, seminar, workshop...) • STAFF: Qualified personnel (qualified personnel exchanges) • LEARN: Learning and training (learning modules, curricula) • INFRA: New or improved infrastructure or facilities • Other
Key results (KER) (does result have a high potential?) You can create a result profile on the Horizon Results Platform (HRP) to promote your KERs and receive D&E	High scientific potential High societal potential (other than climate or environmental) High societal potential High technologic, business or economic potential High policy or regulatory potential N/A

support through Horizon Results
Booster.

Description of the high potential

Audience or target group

- Researcher
- Industry, business partner
- Investor
- EU institutions and/or agencies
- Policy-maker and authorities, international
- Policy-maker and authorities, national
- Policy-maker and authorities, regional
- Citizens
- Standardisation bodies
- Innovators
- End users (practitioners, farmers, etc.)
- Educations/training organization/learners
- Research Infrastructures
- Business accelerator providers
- Other
- Applicable to all

Relevant Stakeholders description

Stakeholders involved in the use of the result. This should include parties already contacted/involved in HFT and exploitation already put forward, for example by direct contact, presentation, take-up of the component. Example: direct customers, direct suppliers, suppliers of complementary products.

Exploitation channel(s)

The main exploitation channels for the results, e.g.,

Possible competitors

Possible competitors in the market offering similar/competing value propositions

Replicability in other domains and ecosystems

Replication capabilities in different domains. They should be as much concrete as possible and based on the bottom-up capability of the partners.

Action plan / Status

Concrete action (plans) for pushing the asset

Steps undertaken towards exploitation

- Prototyping in laboratory environment
- Prototyping in production environment
- Pilot, demonstration or testing
- Intellectual property management
- Licencing to third party
- Complying with regulatory framework
- Contribution to standards
- Feasibility study
- Market study
- Business plan
- Other

Market maturity (state of the market targeted by this result)

- Not yet existing and not clear if market can be created
- Market creating: not existing but potential for the creation of a new market
- Emerging: growing demand, scarce supply
- Mature: the market is already supplied with similar products

5.6. Intellectual Property (IP) Management within the project

WP7 will be responsible for the overall IP monitoring and management within in line with the project's Open Science policy. GA will identify promising results and technologies deriving from project activities that should be protected in a perspective of future commercial exploitation, which will be undertaken with help from each participant's technology transfer office. These offices will be responsible for protection of any relevant intellectual property (IP) rights and solving IP issues related to joint ownership. A simple procedure will be agreed among the partners on how to manage IP, considering Background and Foreground IP rights established with the Consortium Agreement.

The following is an overview of the main points relating to IP considerations within HortiFoodTrends:

- "Background"; i.e., partners' pre-existing know-how, while remaining the sole property of their owners, will be made available to other partners when needed for the project implementation.
- "Foreground"; i.e., knowledge developed during the project will be owned by the partners who have directly contributed to its creation. In case of joint ownership, a separate contract will be established and signed by the co-owners to determine their rights and obligations as well as the IP management and exploitation rules.
- Access rights to Foreground for in-house research or for teaching activities will be granted on a royalty-free basis. Access rights to Foreground and Background brought to the project, if needed for use of a beneficiary's own Foreground including commercialization or for third-party research, will be granted on fair and reasonable conditions.
- Traceability of Background and Foreground information will be sought throughout the project and the flux of Foreground between the partners, and each partner's contribution to the Foreground will be one part of the data which will be recorded.

The consortium is fully committed to the Horizon Europe Open Access to Research Data scheme. Thus, without compromising IPR, the participants will implement a policy of open access and wide dissemination so that research findings are made available as soon as possible to regulators, industry and to the general public, raising public awareness about the new tools and innovative technologies.

6. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION MANAGEMENT STRUCTURE

6.1. Partners' responsibilities

All HortiFoodTrends partners will be actively involved in the implementation of communication and dissemination activities. More specifically, the expected contributions from partners are the following:

- Implementing dissemination activities in their own countries and at European level;
- Exploiting their contacts, networks and channels;
- Supplying news and updates for the web portal and newsletter. Once per month, InHort will share among the consortium a dedicated form to be filled with news and contents that will feed all the on-line channels and the external newsletters;
- Helping to keep the project's Social media accounts alive and active, in particular supporting the development of contents to be communicated and sharing HortiFoodTrends content on their social media channels;
- Managing media relations and distributing press releases;
- Promoting and distributing the newsletter on their websites and through their networks;
- Participating in conferences, workshops, events etc. in order to promote the project and its Outcomes;
- Generating word-of-mouth about the project during meetings and other activities to raise awareness.

6.2. Minimum communication actions for every project partner

Tool	Actions
Website	<p>All partners must include a reference to the project in a permanent page of their respective webpages.</p> <p>The mention will include the following basic information: role of the partner in the project, project description and objectives, consortium, funding and Grant Agreement Number, execution dates and a link to HortiFoodTrends website.</p> <p>All partners will send material (photos and news) to the coordinator for the "News" section of the website.</p>
Social Media	<p>All project partners will follow the social media accounts of the HortiFoodTrends project.</p> <p>When engaging in any DCE action related with the HortiFoodTrend project, project partners are encouraged to post on Social Media using the hashtags of the project and tagging or mentioning (@) the HortiFoodTrend project accounts.</p> <p>The main administrator of the social media accounts is the coordinator, but all partners will prepare content for at least 2 posts per month, according to a schedule provided by InHort.</p>
Newsletter	<p>Each partner will prepare content for the newsletter (text of not more than 250 words). The coordinator will be responsible for preparing and developing 6 topics, the other partners - 2 topics each.</p>
Events participation	<p>Each partner will participate in 1-2 conferences a year during the 3 years of the project (36 months)</p> <p>Each partner will participate in 1 fair during the project, from M12 to M36.</p>
Press releases	<p>Each partner will contact the media and provide at least 1 publication per year during the 3 years of the project (36 months). Examples of publications: Press releases on project results, newspaper articles, interview</p>
Promotional material	<p>Each partner will design and produce/print promotional materials - a project flyer, brochure and poster will be created to generate interest and attention at various events.</p>

6.3. Procedures and monitoring

Once a month, each partner will update the WP6 Leader about the activities implemented in the previous months and, if any, upcoming activities.

Monitoring will be carried out by each partner on a regular basis through an on-line report template **DCE Register** uploaded on the project SharePoint. All consortium partners are encouraged to report the results of each dissemination activity immediately after they are presented.

The reports shall include feedback gathered by the respective partner from the target audience (if applicable), eventually gained contacts to be listed in the contact repository used for further dissemination purposes. All partners are invited to upload the dissemination material (this can be a publication, a conference presentation or the audio file of an interview for example) into project SharePoint [DCE reports](#).

For the purposes of evaluation of project dissemination and communication activities, quantitative indicators and associated metrics were set up where applicable. A numerical target has been estimated as a cumulative estimate based on individual partners' inputs. These targets will be periodically reviewed by the Dissemination WP leader in collaboration with the whole consortium.

7. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES SCHEDULE

The table below provides a preliminary overview of the activities identified in sections 3.2 and 4.2 of the project plan. It is important to note that this is a preliminary plan. As such, it is subject to change throughout the project's duration, as new dissemination opportunities and constraints may emerge. The plan is available here: [HFT_DCE_schedule.xlsx](#).

		M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36		
		cze.24	lip.24	sie.24	wrz.24	paź.24	lis.24	gru.24	sty.25	lut.25	mar.25	kwi.25	maj.25	cze.25	lip.25	sie.25	wrz.25	paź.25	lis.25	gru.25	sty.26	lut.26	mar.26	kwi.26	maj.26	cze.26	lip.26	sie.26	wrz.26	paź.26	lis.26	gru.26	sty.27	lut.27	mar.27	kwi.27	maj.27		
WP1	T.1.1.						InHort				InHort			InHort																									
	T.1.2						InHort				InHort			InHort																									
	T.1.3						InHort				InHort			InHort																									
WP2	T.2.1											UCPH	UCPH																										
	T.2.2																																						
	T.2.3																																						
WP3	T3.1.1																																						
	T3.1.2																																						
	T3.1.3																																						
	T3.2.1																																						
	T3.2.2																																						
WP4	T4.1																																						
	T4.2																																						
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WP5	T5.1																																						
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	T5.3																																						
WP6	T6.1																																						
	T6.2																																						
	T6.3																																						
WP7	T7.1																																						
	T7.2																																						
	T7.3																																						
Workshops at InHort																																							
Deliverables WPG																																							
Scientific articles	No of peer-reviewed scientific articles resulting from the Programme																																						
	KPI 8: No of publications in peer-reviewed journals submitted by the project consortium																																						
	KPI 16: No of articles published by InHort's research departments engaged into project in open access																																						
	KPI 1: No of publications in peer-reviewed journals published by InHort's research departments engaged into project; per year																																						
Events	No of conferences, seminars, fairs, festivals per year																																						
	KPI 19: No of presentations at conferences including oral presentations and posters made by InHort's scientific staff																																						
	No of posts on FB per month																																						
Social	No of posts on Instagram per month																																						
	No of tweets per month																																						
	Newsletter																																						
No of e-material distributed to people at events.																																							
Media - press releases																																							

Figure 1: Initial communication and dissemination activities schedule.

8. OVERVIEW OF DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

So far, the project has been presented at:

- The Festival of Flower, Fruits and Vegetables in Skierniewice,
- The FoodFakty Summit 2024 in Lodz.

Articles have been published in the local media (Radio Łódź, Głos Skierniewic) and on a business portal (sadyogrody.pl). Press materials have described the launch of the project, its aims and objectives.

The Festival of Flower, Fruits and Vegetables in Skierniewice

The Festival of Flower, Fruits and Vegetables in Skierniewice

The FoodFakty Summit 2024 in Lodz

The FoodFakty Summit 2024 in Lodz

9. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable is part of WP6 of the HortiFoodTrends project, the main objective of which is to provide the consortium with practical guidelines for carrying out both internal and external dissemination and communication activities. The Dissemination and Communication Plan outlines the strategy for these activities, detailing the key objectives and messages to be communicated by the project and its participants. It also defines the tools and channels that will be used to reach the identified stakeholders and target audiences.

The Dissemination and Communication Plan presents the strategy for carrying out the dissemination and communication activities, as well as the key objectives and messages to be communicated by the project and its participants, but also outlines the tools and channels that will be used to reach the identified stakeholders and target audiences.

In addition to dissemination, the plan also addresses the exploitation of project results. The consortium will focus on selecting Key Exploitable Results (KERs) based on their significance and potential for innovation in the development of novel HortiFood products. These results will be assessed for their potential impact on stakeholders, including industrial partners and the general public, with a view to exploitation beyond the project timeframe. The plan also includes the establishment of an exploitation register to track the progress of innovations, monitor exploitation plans and explore new commercialisation opportunities.

Also, the plan outlines the documentation and logging of all activities carried out by the project partners, as well as an evaluation process led by the project coordinator, InHort, to assess the progress of the dissemination and communication efforts. The dissemination and communication plan will be continuously monitored and adapted to improve methods of outreach and to ensure wide visibility of the project's activities, results and potential for exploitation.

ANNEX 1 HORTIFOODTRENDS - PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL

Roll-up design and implementation

Leaflet visualisation

Notebook visualisation

